

Melamine trisulfonic acid : An efficient and recyclable catalyst for the synthesis of 2-substituted benzothiazoles in aqueous media

S. Sheik Mansoor*, K. Logaiya, S. P. N. Sudhan, K. Aswin, R. Nasir Ahmed and A. Mohamed Hussain

Bioactive Organic Molecule Synthetic Unit, Research Department of Chemistry, C. Abdul Hakeem College, Melvisharam-632 509, Tamilnadu, India

E-mail : smansoors2000@yahoo.co.in

Manuscript received online 14 January 2014, revised 11 February 2014, accepted 05 April 2014

Abstract : Melamine trisulfonic acid (MTSA) was found to be an efficient and recyclable catalyst for the synthesis of 2-substituted benzothiazoles from aromatic aldehydes and *o*-aminothiophenol in excellent yields in water. This method provides a simple and efficient protocol in terms of mild reaction conditions, clean reaction profiles, small quantity of catalyst, catalyst reusability for several runs and simple workup procedure.

Keywords : Benzothiazoles, melamine trisulfonic acid, *o*-aminothiophenol, aromatic aldehydes, recyclable catalyst.

Introduction

Benzothiazole, a heterocyclic aromatic molecule with electron rich sulfur and nitrogen atoms, exhibit a variety of biological activities, such as antimicrobial activity¹, cytotoxic activity², anti-tubercular activity³, DNA-binding and anticancer activity⁴, anti-breast cancer activity⁵, probes for detecting β -amyloid plaques in Alzheimer's brains⁶, multi-targeted compounds against Alzheimer's disease⁷, novel inhibitors of thrombin and trypsin IV⁸, antiangiogenic activity⁹ and molecular docking activity¹⁰. Further industrial applications as bipolar fluorescent compounds¹¹, blue electroluminescent devices¹² and photosensitizing agents¹³ have also been reported.

Many reports have appeared in the literature describing the formation of benzothiazoles via one of the two major routes. The most commonly used method involves the condensation of *o*-aminothiophenols with substituted nitriles¹⁴, carboxylic acids¹⁵⁻¹⁸, acyl chlorides^{19,20} and esters²¹, or with aldehydes followed by oxidation. Subsequently, because of the availability of a vast number of aldehydes, several improved protocols have been developed for the synthesis of benzothiazoles via the condensation of *o*-aminothiophenol with aldehydes.

Various oxidative reagents and catalysts, such as SDS²², CTAB²³, NaOAc²⁴, HClO₄/PANI²⁵, KAl(SO₄)₂·12H₂O²⁶, iodine²⁷, H₂O₂/HCl²⁸, H₂O₂/CAN²⁹, FeCl₃/

Montmorillonite K-10³⁰, ZnO-beta zeolite³¹ and silica sulfuric acid³² etc. have all been used in the reaction. However, many of these methodologies are associated with one or more disadvantages such as expensive reagents, drastic reaction conditions, low yields, tedious work-up procedures, and co-occurrence of several side reactions. Therefore, a more effective and environmentally friendly process is needed.

Aqua mediated reactions have received considerable attention in organic synthesis due to environmental safety reasons. It would be even more desirable to carry out catalytic organic reactions in water, which normally require delicate reaction conditions in order for the catalyst to be stable and yet reactive. In this context, in recent years much attention has been focused on organic reactions in water, and several reactions of this type have been already identified³³.

Melamine trisulfonic acid has been used as an efficient and reusable catalyst for the solvent free synthesis of coumarins³⁴. Recently, we have reported the application of MTSA for the synthesis of 1,4-dihydropyridine derivatives³⁵, 2,6-dimethyl-4-substituted-1,4-dihydropyridine-3,5-diethyl/dimethylcarboxylate derivatives³⁶ and some fused pyranopyrrole derivatives³⁷. In continuation of our studies, herein, we wish to report the applicability of this reagent on the synthesis of 2-substituted

benzothiazoles in water in the presence of MTSA under thermal condition (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1. Synthesis of 2-substituted benzothiazoles by the reactions of aromatic aldehydes with *o*-aminothiophenol.

Results and discussion

To examine the effect of reaction conditions on the synthesis of 2-substituted benzothiazoles, the condensation of *o*-aminothiophenol (1) and benzaldehyde (2a) was selected as the model reaction.

In the studies regarding the effect of solvents and the amount of the catalyst, the above reaction was conducted in the presence of MTSA (0.05 mmol) with various solvents such as CH₃OH, C₂H₅OH, CH₂Cl₂, CH₃COOC₂H₅, DMF, CH₃CN, THF, CHCl₃, 1,4-dioxane and water at 70 °C. The results indicated that the solvents had a significant effect on the product yield (Table 1). The best conversion was observed when the reaction was performed in water at 70 °C. The yield of 2-phenylbenzothiazole (3a) was 94% (Entry 10) in water at 70 °C.

Moreover, we found that the yields were obviously affected by the amount of MTSA. When 0.02 mmol, 0.03 mmol, and 0.04 mmol, of MTSA were used, the yields were 48, 76 and 82%, respectively (Table 1, Entries 11–13). However, utilizing 0.07 mmol of MTSA did not significantly increase the yield (Table 1, Entry 14). Therefore, 0.05 mmol of MTSA was sufficient. In addition, in the absence of catalyst, the reaction gave an unsatisfactory yield of 2-phenylbenzothiazole (3a) (Table 1, Entry 15). The above results showed that MTSA was essential for high yield, and the best results were obtained when the reaction was carried out with 0.05 mmol of MTSA at 70 °C.

The reusability of the catalyst is one of the most important green aspects by avoiding toxic catalyst³⁸. Thus the recovery and reusability of melamine trisulfonic acid was investigated. After completion of the reaction of *o*-

Table 1. Optimization of the reaction conditions for the synthesis of 2-substituted benzothiazoles by the reactions of aromatic aldehydes with *o*-aminothiophenol solvent screening and catalyst loading^a

Entry	Solvent	Catalyst loading (MTSA mmol)	Time (min)	Yield (%) ^b
1	CH ₃ OH	0.05	60	83
2	C ₂ H ₅ OH	0.05	60	79
3	CH ₂ Cl ₂	0.05	90	73
4	CH ₃ COOC ₂ H ₅	0.05	60	62
5	DMF	0.05	90	68
6	CH ₃ CN	0.05	90	70
7	THF	0.05	90	72
8	CHCl ₃	0.05	90	73
9	1,4-Dioxane	0.05	90	56
10	Water	0.05	48	94
11	Water	0.02	75	48
12	Water	0.03	70	76
13	Water	0.04	60	82
14	Water	0.07	50	94
15	Water	0.00	60	29

^aReaction conditions : benzaldehyde (1 mmol), *o*-aminothiophenol (1 mmol) at 70 °C.

^bIsolated yield.

aminothiophenol (1) and benzaldehyde (2a), the catalyst was separated by filtration, thoroughly washed with ethyl acetate, and dried at room temperature for 4 h. The recycled catalyst could be reused four times without any additional treatment or appreciable reduction in catalytic activity (Fig. 1). The catalyst having recycling performance is also an attractive property for the environmental protection and economic reasons.

To explore the advantages of this MTSA-catalyzed synthesis of 2-substituted benzothiazoles, we compared the results we obtained under the optimized conditions with results reported in the literature by other catalysts (Table 2). Among the solid catalysts like FeCl₃/Montmorillonite K-10³⁰, ZnO-beta zeolite³¹ and silica sulfuric acid³², MTSA was found to be superior in terms of yield and time of reaction.

Under the optimized reaction conditions, a range of 2-substituted benzothiazoles 3a-l were synthesized using 0.05 mmol of MTSA as catalyst at 70 °C. Most products described here have been previously reported in the literature^{22–27}. The condensation of *o*-aminothiophenol with

Fig. 1. Recyclability of MTSA catalyst for the synthesis of 2-substituted benzothiazoles by the reactions of aromatic aldehydes with *o*-aminothiophenol.

Table 2. Comparison of catalytic activity of MTSA with other catalysts reported in the literature for the synthesis of 2-substituted benzothiazoles by the reactions of aromatic aldehydes with *o*-aminothiophenol

Entry	Catalyst	Conditions	Time (h)	Yield (%)	Ref.
1	FeCl ₃ /Montmorillonite K-10	Ultrasound irradiation	1.0	85	30
2	ZnO-beta zeolite	EtOH/reflux	1.0	93	31
3	Silica sulfuric acid	CH ₃ OH/r.t	2.6	86	32
4	MTSA	Water/70 °C	0.8	94	Present work

a series of aromatic aldehydes afforded 2-substituted benzothiazoles in excellent yields catalyzed by 0.05 mmol of MTSA at 70 °C in water. Several electron rich aromatic aldehydes led to the desired products in good yields.

Experimental

Chemicals and apparatus :

Chemicals were purchased from Merck, Fluka and Aldrich Chemical Companies. All yields refer to isolated products unless otherwise stated. ¹H NMR (500 MHz) and ¹³C NMR (125 MHz) spectra were obtained using Bruker DRX-500 Avance at ambient temperature, using TMS as internal standard. FT-IR spectra were obtained as KBr discs on Shimadzu spectrometer. Mass spectra

were determined on a Varion-Saturn 2000 GC/MS instrument. Elemental analysis were measured by means of Perkin-Elmer 2400 CHN elemental analyzer flowchart.

Preparation of melamine trisulfonic acid :

Melamine trisulfonic acid was prepared from melamine and chlorosulfonic acid as reported previously³⁴ (Scheme 2).

General procedure for synthesis of 2-substituted benzothiazoles :

To a mixture of an aromatic aldehyde (1 mmol) and *o*-aminothiophenol (1 mmol) in 5 mL water, MTSA (0.05 mmol) was added and the reaction mixture stirred at 70 °C for 40–65 min. After the reaction was completed, pure

Scheme 2. Preparation of melamine trisulfonic acid.

products were isolated by filtration and washing with hot water and ethanol. In some examples the aqueous mixture was extracted with 10 mL of diethyl ether or ethyl acetate and dried over anhydrous Na_2SO_4 , and the solvent was removed under reduced pressure to give the desired products. The product was analyzed by IR, ^1H NMR, ^{13}C NMR, mass and elemental analysis. Further purification of the product was carried out by short column chromatography on silica gel (hexane/diethyl ether) or crystallization.

Spectral data for the synthesized compounds 3a-l :

2-Phenylbenzothiazole (3a) :

Light yellow crystals; yield 94%; m.p. 112–114 °C (lit.²⁶ m.p. 112–114 °C); IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : 3066, 1585, 1513, 1479, 1286, 1155, 965, 763; ^1H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl_3) δ : 7.36 (1H, t, J 8.2 Hz, Ar-H), 7.49–7.53 (4H, m, Ar-H), 7.88 (1H, d, J 8.0 Hz, Ar-H), 8.08–8.15 (3H, m, Ar-H) ppm; ^{13}C NMR (125 MHz, CDCl_3) δ : 121.0, 123.4, 125.4, 126.1, 127.8, 129.3, 130.6, 134.2, 135.1, 153.0, 169.8 ppm; MS (ESI) : m/z 212 (M+H)⁺; Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_9\text{NS}$: C, 73.93; H, 4.26; N, 6.64; S, 15.17%. Found : C, 73.81; H, 4.23; N, 6.62; S, 15.11%.

2-(4-Chlorophenyl)benzothiazole (3b) :

White crystals; yield 92%; m.p. 113–115 °C (lit.²⁶ m.p. 114–115 °C); IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : 3058, 1593, 1512, 1478, 1434, 1396, 1316, 1286, 1254, 1094, 1014, 824, 752; ^1H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl_3) δ : 7.40–7.43 (2H, m, Ar-H), 7.47 (1H, d, J 8.4 Hz, Ar-H), 7.57–7.62 (1H, m, Ar-H), 7.88 (1H, d, J 8.0 Hz, Ar-H), 8.12 (2H, d, J 8.2 Hz, Ar-H), 8.19 (1H, d, J 8.0 Hz, Ar-H) ppm; ^{13}C NMR (125 MHz, CDCl_3) δ : 120.9, 123.6, 124.9, 126.4, 128.3, 129.5, 131.0, 134.1, 135.3, 153.2, 168.7 ppm; MS (ESI) : m/z 246.45 (M+H)⁺; Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_8\text{ClNS}$: C, 63.56; H, 3.26; N, 5.70; S, 13.03%. Found : C, 63.52; H, 3.24; N, 5.67; S, 12.98%.

2-(4-Hydroxyphenyl)benzothiazole (3c) :

Brown crystals; yield 91%; m.p. 230–232 °C (lit.²² m.p. 231 °C); IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : 3342, 3060, 2996, 1606, 1544, 1383, 1313, 1282, 1166, 1106, 1076, 976, 757; ^1H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl_3) δ : 7.04–7.12 (2H, m, Ar-H), 7.33–7.38 (1H, m, Ar-H), 7.48–7.52 (1H, m, Ar-H), 7.79 (2H, d, J 8.2 Hz, Ar-H), 7.88 (1H, d, J 8.0 Hz, Ar-H), 8.08 (1H, d, J 8.0 Hz, Ar-H), 9.86 (1H, s, OH) ppm; ^{13}C NMR (125 MHz, CDCl_3) δ : 121.2, 123.8, 125.2, 126.2, 128.0, 129.7, 130.7, 134.0, 135.5, 153.1, 169.6 ppm; MS (ESI) : m/z 228 (M+H)⁺; Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_9\text{NSO}$: C, 68.72; H, 3.96; N, 6.17; S, 14.10%. Found : C, 68.66; H, 3.94; N, 6.14; S, 14.11%.

2-(4-Methylphenyl)benzothiazole (3d) :

White crystals; yield 94%; m.p. 82–84 °C (lit.²⁶ m.p. 83 °C); IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : 3053, 3023, 1603, 1485, 1318, 1289, 1250, 1122, 953, 834, 766; ^1H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl_3) δ : 2.42 (3H, s, CH_3), 7.22 (2H, d, J 8.2 Hz, Ar-H), 7.35–7.40 (1H, m, Ar-H), 7.51–7.54 (1H, m, Ar-H), 7.82 (1H, d, J 8.2 Hz, Ar-H), 8.08 (2H, d, J 8.0 Hz, Ar-H), 8.14 (1H, d, J 8.0 Hz, Ar-H) ppm; ^{13}C NMR (125 MHz, CDCl_3) δ : 21.6, 120.7, 123.2, 124.8, 126.0, 128.2, 129.1, 131.1, 134.5, 135.2, 153.0, 169.5 ppm; MS (ESI) : m/z 226 (M+H)⁺; Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{11}\text{NS}$: C, 74.67; H, 4.89; N, 6.22; S, 14.22%. Found : C, 74.62; H, 4.84; N, 6.17; S, 14.18%.

2-(4-Methoxyphenyl)benzothiazole (3e) :

Light yellow crystals; yield 96%; m.p. 120–122 °C (lit.²² m.p. 121 °C); IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : 3071, 2990, 2933, 1602, 1590, 1554, 1522, 1483, 1434, 1413, 1310, 1305, 1289, 1252, 1226, 1180, 1170, 1025, 965, 793; ^1H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl_3) δ : 3.77 (3H, s, OCH_3), 7.06–7.08 (2H, m, Ar-H), 7.31–7.34 (1H, m, Ar-H), 7.46–7.48 (1H, m, Ar-H), 7.94 (1H, d, J 8.1 Hz, Ar-H), 8.11–8.13 (3H, m, Ar-H) ppm; ^{13}C NMR (125 MHz, CDCl_3) δ :

54.9, 121.5, 122.9, 125.0, 126.1, 127.7, 129.4, 130.8, 133.9, 135.4, 152.5, 168.9 ppm; MS (ESI) : m/z 242 (M+H)⁺; Anal. Calcd. for C₁₄H₁₁NSO : C, 69.71; H, 4.56; N, 5.81; S, 13.28%. Found : C, 69.67; H, 4.52; N, 5.77; S, 13.24%.

2-(4-Nitrophenyl)benzothiazole (3f) :

Light yellow crystals; yield 85%; m.p. 230–232 °C (lit.²³ m.p. 231–232 °C); IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) : 3066, 2996, 2936, 1602, 1592, 1552, 1463, 1416, 1318, 1309, 1280, 1223, 1075, 1025, 965, 788; ¹H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 7.06–7.07 (2H, m, Ar-H), 7.33–7.35 (1H, m, Ar-H), 7.44–7.46 (1H, m, Ar-H), 7.92 (1H, d, *J* 8.2 Hz, Ar-H), 8.04–8.06 (3H, m, Ar-H) ppm; ¹³C NMR (125 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 120.8, 122.7, 124.7, 126.6, 127.8, 129.5, 131.2, 133.8, 135.6, 152.7, 168.8 ppm; MS (ESI) : m/z 257 (M+H)⁺; Anal. Calcd. for C₁₃H₈N₂SO₂ : C, 60.94; H, 3.13; N, 10.94; S, 12.50%. Found : C, 60.88; H, 3.07; N, 10.88; S, 12.52%.

2-(4-N,N-Dimethylphenyl)benzothiazole (3g) :

Light yellow crystals; yield 90%; m.p. 174–176 °C (lit.²² m.p. 173 °C); IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) : 3055, 2895, 2807, 1608, 1579, 1540, 1506, 1439, 1360, 1310, 1288, 1066, 965, 757; ¹H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 3.07 (6H, s, CH₃), 7.00–7.03 (2H, m, Ar-H), 7.34–7.36 (1H, m, Ar-H), 7.44–7.47 (1H, m, Ar-H), 7.89 (1H, d, *J* 8.2 Hz, Ar-H), 7.98–8.00 (2H, m, Ar-H), 8.05 (1H, d, *J* 8.2 Hz, Ar-H) ppm; ¹³C NMR (125 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 40.4, 121.3, 123.8, 125.5, 126.5, 127.5, 129.6, 131.3, 134.2, 135.0, 152.9, 169.0 ppm; MS (ESI) : m/z 255 (M+H)⁺; Anal. Calcd. for C₁₅H₁₄N₂S : C, 70.87; H, 5.51; N, 11.02; S, 12.60%. Found : C, 70.77; H, 5.50; N, 11.00; S, 12.57%.

2-(2-Chlorophenyl)benzothiazole (3h) :

White crystals; yield 90%; m.p. 80–82 °C (lit.²⁴ m.p. 81–82 °C); IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) : 3066, 1588, 1499, 1433, 1311, 1250, 1061, 1018, 966, 755; ¹H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 7.38–7.41 (3H, m, Ar-H), 7.56–7.59 (2H, m, Ar-H), 7.88 (1H, d, *J* 8.0 Hz, Ar-H), 8.12 (1H, d, *J* 8.2 Hz, Ar-H), 8.26–8.28 (1H, m, Ar-H) ppm; ¹³C NMR (125 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 120.9, 123.1, 124.7, 125.9, 127.7, 129.3, 130.9, 134.4, 135.3, 152.4, 170.2 ppm; MS (ESI) : m/z 246.45 (M+H)⁺; Anal. Calcd. for C₁₃H₈ClNS : C, 63.56; H, 3.26; N, 5.70; S, 13.03%. Found : C, 63.55; H, 3.23; N, 5.71; S, 13.00%.

2-(2-Hydroxyphenyl)benzothiazole (3i) :

White crystals; yield 81%; m.p. 130–132 °C (lit.²⁷ m.p. 129–131 °C); IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) : 3312, 3060, 2922, 1620, 1584, 1520, 1480, 1450, 1314, 1274, 1254, 1039, 972, 740; ¹H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 7.02–7.04 (1H, m, Ar-H), 7.16 (1H, dd, *J*₁ 8.0 Hz, *J*₂ 1.0 Hz, Ar-H), 7.32–7.36 (2H, m, Ar-H), 7.48–7.51 (1H, m, Ar-H), 7.78 (1H, dd, *J*₁ 7.8 Hz, *J*₂ 1.2 Hz, Ar-H), 7.88 (1H, d, *J* 7.8 Hz, Ar-H), 8.04 (1H, d, *J* 8.2 Hz, Ar-H), 10.44 (1H, s, OH) ppm; ¹³C NMR (125 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 121.5, 123.0, 125.0, 125.8, 128.2, 129.4, 130.5, 133.0, 135.6, 152.6, 170.0 ppm; MS (ESI) : m/z 228 (M+H)⁺; Anal. Calcd. for C₁₃H₉NSO : C, 68.72; H, 3.96; N, 6.17; S, 14.10%. Found : C, 68.62; H, 3.93; N, 6.18; S, 14.06%.

2-(2-Methoxyphenyl)benzothiazole (3j) :

Light yellow crystals; yield 94%; m.p. 118–120 °C (lit.²³ m.p. 120–122 °C); IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) : 3044, 3011, 2966, 1614, 1598, 1584, 1522, 1494, 1460, 1429, 1306, 1286, 1255, 1160, 1011, 966, 945, 753; ¹H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 3.78 (3H, s, OCH₃), 7.04 (1H, d, *J* 8.2 Hz, Ar-H), 7.14 (1H, t, *J* 7.2 Hz, Ar-H), 7.44 (1H, t, *J* 7.2 Hz, Ar-H), 7.48–7.54 (2H, m, Ar-H), 7.92 (1H, d, *J* 8.0 Hz, Ar-H), 8.14 (1H, d, *J* 8.2 Hz, Ar-H), 8.28 (1H, dd, *J*₁ 7.8 Hz, *J*₂ 1.2 Hz, Ar-H) ppm; ¹³C NMR (125 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 55.7, 120.9, 123.6, 124.8, 125.7, 128.1, 129.1, 131.0, 134.3, 135.7, 152.8, 170.1 ppm; MS (ESI) : m/z 242 (M+H)⁺; Anal. Calcd. for C₁₄H₁₁NSO : C, 69.71; H, 4.56; N, 5.81; S, 13.28%. Found : C, 69.61; H, 4.53; N, 5.83; S, 13.26%.

2-(3-Chlorophenyl)benzothiazole (3k) :

White crystals; yield 91%; m.p. 96–98 °C (lit.²⁵ m.p. 94–95 °C); IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) : 3059, 1629, 1584, 1564, 1541, 1504, 1474, 1459, 1435, 1425, 1295, 1266, 1164, 1073, 943, 782; ¹H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 7.33–7.35 (2H, m, Ar-H), 7.46–7.48 (1H, m, Ar-H), 7.56–7.58 (1H, m, Ar-H), 7.86 (1H, d, *J* 8.2 Hz, Ar-H), 7.96–7.97 (1H, m, Ar-H), 8.06 (1H, d, *J* 8.2 Hz, Ar-H), 8.16 (1H, t, *J* 7.2 Hz, Ar-H) ppm; ¹³C NMR (125 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 121.3, 123.3, 125.2, 126.0, 127.7, 129.0, 131.3, 134.2, 135.5, 153.1, 169.3 ppm; MS (ESI) : m/z 246.45 (M+H)⁺; Anal. Calcd. for C₁₃H₈ClNS : C, 63.56; H, 3.26; N, 5.70; S, 13.03%. Found : C, 63.45; H, 3.22; N, 5.72; S, 13.04%.

2-(3-Nitrophenyl)benzothiazole (31) :

Light yellow crystals; yield 84%; m.p. 186–188 °C (lit.²³ m.p. 185–186 °C); IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) : 3077, 1622, 1593, 1558, 1477, 1431, 1361, 1341, 1314, 1284, 1126, 1104, 984, 766; ¹H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 7.38 (1H, t, *J* 7.2 Hz, Ar-H), 7.50 (1H, t, *J* 7.2 Hz, Ar-H), 7.70 (1H, t, *J* 7.2 Hz, Ar-H), 7.92 (1H, d, *J* 8.2 Hz, Ar-H), 8.12 (1H, d, *J* 8.2 Hz, Ar-H), 8.32 (1H, dd, *J*₁ 8.2 Hz, *J*₂ 1.2 Hz, Ar-H), 8.44 (1H, d, *J* 8.0 Hz, Ar-H), 8.66 (1H, s, Ar-H) ppm; ¹³C NMR (125 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 121.2, 123.2, 124.9, 126.2, 127.9, 129.3, 130.7, 134.1, 135.2, 153.3, 168.6 ppm; MS (ESI) : *m/z* 257 (M+H)⁺; Anal. Calcd. for C₁₃H₈N₂SO₂ : C, 60.94; H, 3.13; N, 10.94; S, 12.50%. Found : C, 60.84; H, 3.10; N, 10.93; S, 12.44%.

Conclusions

In summary, we have found an efficient and practical procedure for the preparation of 2-substituted benzothiazoles in the presence of MTSA under thermal condition. This methodology offers the mild reaction conditions, enhanced reaction rates, clean reaction profiles, operational and experimental simplicity, high yields, an inexpensive and easily available reagent and with options of further transformations of the resulting benzothiazoles into synthetically interesting biologically active compounds. Hence, this synthetic methodology is ideally suited for automated applications in organic synthesis.

Acknowledgements

The authors are thankful to the Management of C. Abdul Hakeem College, Melvisharam Tamilnadu, India for the facilities and support.

References

1. M. K. Singh, R. Tilak, G. Nath, S. K. Awasthi and A. Agarwal, *Euro. J. Med. Chem.*, 2013, **63**, 635.
2. R. M. Kumbhare, T. Dadmal, U. Kosurkar, V. Sridhar and J. V. Rao, *Bioorg. Med. Chem. Lett.*, 2012, **22**, 453.
3. V. N. Telvekar, V. K. Bairwa, K. Satardekar and A. Bellubi, *Bioorg. Med. Chem. Lett.*, 2012, **22**, 649.
4. A. Kamal, K. S. Reddy, M. N. A. Khan, R. V. C. R. N. C. Shetti, M. J. Ramaiah, S. N. C. V. L. Pushpavalli, C. Srinivas, M. Pal-Bhadra, M. Chourasia, G. N. Sastry, A. Juvekar, S. Zingde and M. Barkume, *Bioorg. Med. Chem.*, 2010, **18**, 4747.
5. V. R. Solomon, C. Hu and H. Lee, *Bioorg. Med. Chem.*, 2009, **17**, 7585.
6. M. Ono, S. Hayashi, H. Kimura, H. Kawashima, M. Nakayama and H. Saji, *Bioorg. Med. Chem.*, 2009, **17**, 7002.
7. R. S. Keri, C. Quintanova, S. M. Marques, A. R. Esteves, S. M. Cardoso and M. A. Santos, *Bioorg. Med. Chem.*, 2013, **21**, 4559.
8. M. Karle, W. Knecht and Y. Xue, *Bioorg. Med. Chem. Lett.*, 2012, **22**, 4839.
9. S. Nagarajan, S. Majumder, U. Sharma, S. Rajendran, N. Kumar, S. Chatterjee and B. Singh, *Bioorg. Med. Chem. Lett.*, 2013, **23**, 287.
10. K. M. Khan, F. Rahim, S. A. Halim, M. Taha, M. Khan, S. Perveen, Zaheer-ul-Haq, M. A. Mesaik and M. I. Choudhary, *Bioorg. Med. Chem.*, 2011, **19**, 4286.
11. H. Wang, G. Chen, X. Xu, H. Chen and S. Ji, *Dyes and Pigments*, 2010, **86**, 238.
12. H.-Y. Fu, X.-Y. Sun, X.-d. Gao, F. Xiao and B.-X. Shao, *Synthetic Metals*, 2009, **159**, 254.
13. W.-P. Hu, Y.-K. Chen, C.-C. Liao, H.-S. Yu, Y.-M. Tsai, S.-M. Huang, F.-Y. Tsai, H.-C. Shen, L.-S. Chang and J.-J. Wang, *Bioorg. Med. Chem.*, 2010, **18**, 6197.
14. R. H. Tale, *Org. Lett.*, 2002, **4**, 1641.
15. S. Mourtas, D. Gatos and K. Barlos, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2001, **42**, 2201.
16. A. K. Chakraborti, C. Selvam, G. Kaur and S. Bhagat, *Synlett.*, 2004, 851.
17. C. P. Chen and Y. J. Chen, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2004, **45**, 113.
18. J. A. Seijas, M. P. Vazquez-Tato, M. R. Carballido-Reboredo, J. Crecente-Campo and L. Romar-Lopez, *Synlett.*, 2007, 313.
19. I. R. Laskar and T. M. Chen, *Chemistry of Materials*, 2004, **16**, 111.
20. R. N. Nadaf, S. A. Siddiqui, T. Daniel, R. J. Lahoti and K. V. Srinivasan, *J. Mol. Catal. A : Chem.*, 2004, **214**, 155.
21. H. Matsushita, S. H. Lee, M. Joung, B. Clapham and K. D. Janda, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2004, **45**, 313.
22. K. Bahrami, M. M. Khodaei and A. Nejatia, *Green Chem.*, 2010, **12**, 1237.
23. X. L. Yang, C. M. Xu, S. M. Lin, J. X. Chen, J. C. Ding, H. Y. Wu and W. K. Su, *J. Braz. Chem. Soc.*, 2010, **21**, 37.
24. M. Okimoto, T. Yoshida, M. Hoshi, K. Hattori, M. Komata, K. Tomozawa and T. Chiba, *Heterocycles*, 2008, **75**, 35.
25. M. Abdollahi-Alibeik and S. Poorirani, *Phosphorus, Sulfur, and Silicon and the Related Elements*, 2009, **184**, 3182.

26. S. S. Pawar, D. V. Dekhane, M. S. Shingare and S. N. Thore, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 2008, **61**, 905.
27. Y. Li, Y. L. Wang and J. Y. Wang, *Chem. Lett.*, 2006, **35**, 460.
28. H. Y. Guo, J. C. Li and Y. L. Shang, *Chin. Chem. Lett.*, 2009, **20**, 1408.
29. K. Bahrami, M. M. Khodaei and F. Naali, *J. Org. Chem.*, 2008, **73**, 6835.
30. G.-F. Chen, H.-M. Jia, L.-Y. Zhang, B.-H. Chen and J.-T. Li, *Ultrason. Sonochem.*, 2013, **20**, 627.
31. S. S. Katkar, P. H. Mohite, L. S. Gadekar, K. N. Vidhate and M. K. Lande, *Chin. Chem. Lett.*, 2010, **21**, 421.
32. G. F. Chen, L. Y. Zhang, H. M. Jia, B. H. Chen, J. T. Li, S. X. Wang and G. Y. Bai, *Res. Chem. Intermed.*, 2013, **39**, 2077.
33. N. Azizi, A. K. Amiri, R. Baghi, M. Bolourtchian and M. M. Hashemi, *Monatsh. Chem.*, 2009, **140**, 1471.
34. F. Shirini, M. A. Zolfigol and J. Albadi, *J. Iran. Chem. Soc.*, 2010, **7**, 895.
35. K. Aswin, K. Logaiya, S. P. N. Sudhan and S. S. Mansoor, *J. Taibah Univ. Sci.*, 2012, **6**, 1.
36. S. S. Mansoor, K. Aswin, K. Logaiya and S. P. N. Sudhan, *J. King Saud University-Sci.*, 2013, **25**, 191.
37. S. S. Mansoor, K. Aswin, K. Logaiya, S. P. N. Sudhan and H. Ramadoss, *J. Saudi Chem. Soc.*, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jscs.2012.12.009>.
38. A. Patra and T. Mahapatra, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2012, **89**, 925.

